

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: HOLDER****FIRST NAME: ALISON****PROGRAM CODE: DME****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show the actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references.

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 0%

The author used the following software: MSWord 365 on Windows 10

List your 7 key concepts with the page number in the text (then bold these terms in your RP):

1. Researching the Topic (EUCLID 2021, 8)
2. Writing the Essay (EUCLID 2021, 11)
3. Editing the Essay (EUCLID 2021, 12)
4. Punctuation and Syntax (EUCLID 2021, 26)
5. American vs. British English (EUCLID 2021, 28)
6. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 36)
7. Start early (EUCLID 2021, 7)

QUALITY ASSURANCE IN ACADEMIC WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

In the field of project management, quality assurance is a critical aspect of all the processes within the methodology. Reviewing the course material for ACA401D, I recognize that the process of preparing, writing, and submitting an academic paper has quality assurance procedures and tools. I will argue that quality assurance shares a similar weighting to researching and writing an academic paper. Without quality assurance, a writer can easily and unintentionally plagiarize when arguing a perspective. In this scenario, previously encountered phrases can escape the subconscious and be written as though they are the writer's original thoughts.

This response paper highlights the best practices, according to Euclid University (2021, 3), for essay construction and compliance.

2) THE ASSURANCE PATHWAY

I subscribe to the thought that the outcome should be as desired when you understand a methodology and apply it as designed in the applicable circumstances. It is clear to me that this opinion is most likely to hold in the writing and submission of an academic paper within the Euclid University context. The recommended pathway identifies that the writer should have a topic in mind to guide your actions in executing the academic exercise being discussed. Then, you must engage in research to inform your position on the topic and to guide your organizing of the information. The process intensifies as you begin to write the essay while being mindful of citing sources of varying types and allowing yourself sufficient time to rest and edit the essay (EUCLID 2021, 7).

In the next section, I will summarize the value of research and its relationship to the quality of what is written in the essay.

a) **Researching the Topic and Writing the Essay**

I have chosen to explore the topics of researching the topic and writing the essay as one aspect because of the input-output relationship between the two activities. The quality and diversity of the results from the research are inputs to the actual essay. The depth of research determines the degree of profundity that the essay will convey. A valuable point that was made regarding research is to include your existing knowledge of the topic in your research notes (EUCLID 2021, 8). In my experience, students are directed to use expert writing, which equates to using only knowledge other than your own. While conducting research for the essay, including differing views and arguments is advantageous. This critical analysis approach will allow you to better validate your argument as you examine the pros and cons of the topic by demonstrating that an objective lens was used in the formulation of your conclusion (EUCLID 2021, 9).

With a depth of information gathered through an objective lens, you can organize your thoughts and begin to write the essay. Bearing the standard format for an essay (Euclid 2021, 10), the first draft is written. It would be efficient to consider grammar, **punctuation, and syntax** (EUCLID 2021, 26), even though it takes more time to be deliberate in your writing. The time taken in the first draft will be saved in re-working the essay during the editing and instructor review stages.

Quality assurance refers to incorporating quality controls in the process rather than having several points of quality checks; the latter results in more re-work, which carries an opportunity cost on time. Creating a draft essay is a good quality assurance mechanism, especially when combined with continuous self-review. Another valuable quality assurance mechanism is “putting the essay aside for a few days” (Euclid 2021, 11) so that the editing is done with a clear mind.

b) Editing the Essay

After resting on an essay, the writer must review the essay to ensure that the paragraphs treat the topic and the question being investigated. The editing process also checks for consistency regarding the use of the English style, whether American or British. This is important as most Microsoft Word processing software defaults to American English. Therefore, you must review to ensure that when a style is declared, it is maintained.

In editing the essay, you are also checking the quality of the work to ensure that it meets the requirements of the assignment, such as word limit or the number of topics to be covered in the essay. (Euclid 2021, 12). This aspect of editing addresses compliance with the submission requirements rather than compliance with academic standards. Though it is not directly related to the quality of the content, it relates to meeting the comprehensive requirements of the submission (EUCLID 2021, 12).

The next two sections of this essay will look at considerations when choosing the style of English to be used and those to avoid plagiarism when editing an essay.

i) *American vs British English*

The default setting in Microsoft Word for English is United States or American English. Though it can be customized for UK or British English, this setting resets to the default of American English when system updates are done. It is, therefore, prudent to check the z and s spelling, as this is one of the most common differences between the two styles. The Americans use “z” and the British use “s” for words such as realize. Additionally, there are words with the same spelling but different interpretations in these two cultural contexts. In the UK, the word “mates” refers to best friends, while in the US, the same word refers to a lover, particularly in a civil union (EUCLID 2021, 28).

ii) *Plagiarism*

Due to the gravity of the penalties for acts of plagiarism, it is in your best interest, as a writer, to ensure that you are not committing this offense. The editing process allows you to step back from the essay and reflect on whether specific phrases are yours or can be attributed to others, even if you are paraphrasing (EUCLID 2021, 36). An additional quality assurance tool is online programs such as Grammarly or Turn It In which scan the text for the level of plagiarism and provide a percentage of plagiarism result. From my knowledge, a plagiarism result of 10% or more would deem the essay to be non-admissible for plagiarism.

The level of intent and effort that is required for academic papers due to the multiplicity of considerations to meet quality standards, has been laid out in the study material for ACA-401D. Plagiarism is the most serious of all the possible infractions that can be committed in writing an essay. One that this writer intends to avoid by following the quality assurance procedures of the university.

3) CONCLUSION

After reading the study guide and reviewing other student tools, I have a greater understanding of the requirements for preparing and submitting an academic paper. There are no major or minor activities in this activity. Whether it is researching the topic and writing the essay or editing the essay, you must approach it with meticulous intent. You must also be mindful of the reviewer and avoid several feedback iterations.

One lesson I have learned from this specific essay writing exercise is that you must **start early** to prepare and write a quality academic paper or essay (EUCLID 2021, 7). The challenge with time was specifically about technology risks. For example, I experienced a “run error” with the Zotero extension tab in Microsoft Word. It did not permit citation or bibliography insertions as outlined. It took considerable time to troubleshoot this, resulting in undue strain in preparation for this assignment.

In addition to all the other quality assurance tools that have been validated as critical to a compliant submission, it is necessary to have a realistic schedule for essay writing efforts. This combination of tools and techniques will reap good outcomes.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2021. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth ed. Bangui: Euclid University.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.